

Volatile Resistive Switching Memory Based on Ag Ion Drift/Diffusion Part I: Numerical Modeling

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Abstract—Resistive-switching random access memory (RRAM) devices based on filamentary switching are attracting widespread interest for their unique properties, such as high ON-OFF ratio, ultrasteep slope, good endurance, and low-current operation. Recently, volatile RRAMs based on Ag drift and diffusion were also demonstrated for possible applications such as crosspoint array selectors and neuromorphic computing. However, the mechanism of the volatile switching, namely, the spontaneous dissolution of the Ag filament, is still not clear. A deep understanding of the metallic filament formation and spontaneous disruption would strongly help the engineering of the device for optimized performances. Here, we present a numerical physics-based drift/diffusion modeling framework to describe the threshold switching, I - V characteristics, and morphological evolution of the metallic filament. The model can support TCAD-type device simulations for scaling, reliability, and variability studies.

Index Terms—Crosspoint array, diffusion model, selector device, surface self-diffusion, volatile switching.

I. INTRODUCTION

RESISTIVE-switching random access memory (RRAM) devices [1]–[3] are receiving strong interest as a future-generation high-density storage technology. Thanks to their nanoscale size and two-terminal configuration, RRAM devices can be arranged in area-efficient 3-D crosspoint arrays. However, select devices are needed in RRAM arrays to efficiently access each individual storage cell without parasitic

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sneak path currents and disturbs [4], [5]. To this purpose, one selector/one resistor (1S1R) schemes provide a promising alternative solution for crosspoint arrays. Recently, selector devices based on volatile RRAMs have been proposed, and high ON-OFF ratio, fast switching speed, short relaxation time, and high ON-current density have been demonstrated [6]–[8]. The switching to the ON-state and recovery to the OFF-state are believed to be resulting from the metallic filament (e.g., Cu or Ag nanoscale filament) formation and disruption [9], [10], respectively. However, the fundamental mechanisms of filament formation and disruption are not clear yet.

In this paper, we present a thermally activated drift/diffusion model based on Monte Carlo simulations of Ag nanoparticle (NP) Brownian-like motion, which can predict the asymmetric forming and I - V characteristics of our Ag/SiO_x/C device. High ON-OFF ratio and threshold switching in the I - V curves are also predicted by the simulated results. We also introduce a surface self-diffusion model to describe the detailed evolution of the filament during the spontaneous transition to the OFF-state. The relaxation time of the device can be predicted as the filament disconnection time, which is found to be highly sensitive to the filament size.

A preliminary study of the physics-based modeling of the volatile device was previously reported in [11], where a size-dependent relaxation time model for the volatile process was employed. Here, we provide an extensive analysis of the physical basis and the driving forces of the volatile behavior with the help of Gibbs-Thomson effect and surface self-diffusion effect, and the development of the size-dependent relaxation time, which will provide the basis for the analytical model in the companion paper [12].

II. EXPERIMENTAL SAMPLES AND SETUP

Fig. 1(a) shows a schematic of the volatile RRAM addressed in this paper, consisting of an Ag/SiO_x/C stack. To facilitate the electrical characterization, the RRAM is connected to an integrated transistor via the W bottom contact. The bottom electrode (BE) is a graphitic carbon (C) pillar with a diameter of 70 nm. The SiO_x ($x \approx 1$) switching layer with the thickness of 5 nm, and the Ag top electrode (TE) with the thickness of 50 nm were deposited by e-beam evaporation without breaking the vacuum [13]. A mixed dc/ac experimental setup was used for the electrical characterization of the

Fig. 1. (a) Schematic of the Ag/SiO_x/C RRAM volatile resistive switching device. (b) Sketch of the CF structure where positive-voltage forming and successive retraction of the CF results in the formation of a BE reservoir, enabling bidirectional switching from both electrode sides.

Fig. 2. Experimental and calculated characteristics of (a) asymmetric forming process and (b) bidirectional volatile switching of the volatile RRAM device.

volatile RRAM [14]. The experimental dc characteristics were collected by a semiconductor parameter analyzer HP4156, while ac characteristics were obtained by a TTI-TGA 12102 arbitrary waveform generator and the Lecroy Waverunner oscilloscope with 600-MHz bandwidth.

III. EXPERIMENTAL CHARACTERISTICS

A. Asymmetric Forming

Fig. 1(b) shows an atomistic sketch of the forming operation, where Ag ions drift from the TE to the BE in response to the application of a positive voltage to the TE [4], [13]. Due to the asymmetric structure of our devices, a negative voltage applied to the TE could not lead to the filament formation. This is shown in **Fig. 2(a)**, showing the current–voltage (I – V) characteristics during a first negative-voltage sweep followed by a positive-voltage sweep. No forming event can be observed at negative voltage due to the inert property of bottom graphite electrode, while forming clearly appears as a steep increase of the current for a positive TE voltage $V_{TE} = 3$ V. Note that the forming process is volatile, namely the device spontaneously switches to the OFF-state as V_{TE} decays to zero. This can be understood by the spontaneous retraction of the Ag filament after forming [**Fig. 1(b)**].

B. Bidirectional Volatile Switching

After the positive forming, bidirectional threshold switching is observed, as shown in **Fig. 2(b)**. Here, the application of a positive voltage causes switching to the ON-state at a

characteristic threshold voltage V_{T+} of about 1.75 V, which is significantly lower than the forming voltage. The device then switches back to the OFF-state as the voltage is reduced to zero. The following sweep at negative voltage causes switching at a threshold V_{T-} of about -0.3 V. The negative switching can be understood by the presence of residual Ag clusters at the BE [**Fig. 1(b)**] after the spontaneous dissolution of the filament by the initial forming. This residual Ag can serve as a reservoir for the migration of Ag ions under a negative V_{TE} , thus supporting bidirectional switching of the volatile RRAM. The switching is also volatile after switching at a negative voltage. Notably, the switching characteristics in **Fig. 2** show an ON–OFF ratio larger than 10^7 between an ON-state current of $50 \mu\text{A}$ and an OFF-state current below 5 pA, i.e., the minimum sensitivity in our experimental setup [15].

IV. DRIFT/DIFFUSION MODEL

A. Monte Carlo Model

The residual Ag at the BE side after the filament dissolution results from the adhesion of Ag to the C electrode driven by the tendency to minimize the interfacial energy [16], [17]. To describe the surface energy minimization, we adopt the Gibbs–Thomson interfacial potential energy [18], given by:

$$U(x) = -\omega_I \exp\left(-\frac{(x - x_C)^2}{R_I^2}\right) \quad (1)$$

where x is the position along with the switching layer from the TE to the BE, x_C is the location of the clustering center, and ω_I and R_I are the amplitude and the principal radius of the potential profile, respectively. We assumed N mobile Ag NPs between the two electrodes that can diffuse by Brownian-like motion. This can be expressed by the Langevin equation [17], namely

$$\eta \frac{dx_i}{dt} = \alpha F - \frac{\partial U(x_i)}{\partial x_i} + \sqrt{2\eta k_B T} \zeta_i \quad (2)$$

where x_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, N$) is the position of the i th NP at time t and η is the NP viscosity in the insulating material. The first term on the right-hand side of (2) describes the drift effect of the electric field $F = [V(t) - V_s]/L$ on the NP with induced charge α , where $V(t)$ is the externally applied voltage at time t , V_s is an empirical parameter denoting the voltage dropping outside of the active region, and L is the distance between the two electrodes. The second term represents the driving force of interfacial energy, while the third term gives the temperature-induced thermal fluctuation of the particle position, where k_B is the Boltzmann's constant, T is the temperature, and ζ_i is given by a Gaussian white noise generator.

The temperature dynamics can be described by Newton's law of cooling:

$$\frac{dT}{dt} = C_T \frac{V(t)^2}{R_S} - \kappa(T - T_0) \quad (3)$$

where C_T and κ are the heat capacitance and heat transfer coefficient, respectively, and T_0 is the ambient temperature,

Fig. 3. Ag NPs distribution during (a) negative forming, (b) positive forming, and (c) threshold switching. Circles: position of Ag NPs. Lines: statistical probability of the NP being at the position. Circled numbers: states corresponding to the bias points in Fig. 2.

which was assumed to be 300 K in our experiments and simulations. The Joule heating power $V(t)^2/R_S$ is directly related to the resistance R_S of the volatile RRAM, which is calculated as the summation of all tunneling resistances between adjacent Ag NPs, namely:

$$R_S = \sum_{i=0}^N R_t \exp\left(\frac{x_{i+1} - x_i}{l_t}\right) / (1 + \beta F) \quad (4)$$

where R_t is the tunneling resistance amplitude, l_t is the effective tunneling length, and $x_0 = -L/2$ and $x_{N+1} = L/2$ are the positions of the TE and BE, respectively. The term $1 + \beta F$ indicates the Poole–Frenkel effect of field-induced barrier lowering [19], where β describes the barrier lowering effect of the electric field.

B. Simulation Results

Fig. 2(a) shows the simulated I – V curves for the forming process, while Fig. 3(a) and (b) shows the simulated distribution profile of the Ag NPs ($N = 60$) in normalized position (x/L), for each of the bias points ①–⑥ indicated in the figure. Initially, all NPs are located at the TE. The application of a negative voltage ① does not cause any change in the NP position ②, thus no forming event takes place. This is because the electric field suppresses the diffusion of Ag NPs induced by the thermal fluctuation. The application of a positive voltage ③ leads instead to a field-driven drift of the Ag NP in correspondence of $V_{T+} = 3$ V, thus resulting in a marked increase of the conductance due to the broadly distributed profile of the NPs ④. Note that the increase of conductance causes significant Joule heating, thus causing positive feedback, hence, the rapid diffusion of the NPs across the insulator layer and consequent switching to the ON-state. The physical positive feedback is counterbalanced by the external compliance current I_C causing negative feedback via the voltage snapback [20]. As the applied voltage is decreased toward zero, the Ag NPs spontaneously retract to the TE and the BE to minimize the interfacial energy ⑤, ⑥.

Fig. 2(b) shows the simulated I – V curves for the bidirectional switching, and Fig. 3(c) shows the corresponding NP distribution. Since Ag NPs are now left at both TE and BE sides, switching to the ON-state can now take place independent of the bias polarity [21]. For instance, the application of a positive voltage ⑦ induces the migration of Ag ions and the

consequent filament formation ⑧, followed by relaxation to minimize the interface energy ⑨, ⑩. The same happens for an applied negative voltage above a certain threshold.

Table I provides a summary of the parameter values used in the simulations. All these values are in reasonable agreement with the range reported in the literature [17], [22]. The difference between forming and switching parameters can be attributed to changes induced by the forming operation, which are related to the residual Ag NPs. Also, different V_s values were used to account for the asymmetry of bidirectional switching after forming. The asymmetry threshold of bidirectional switching can be understood as the difference of top/bottom electrode-insulator Schottky barriers (see the definition of V_s) which reduce the effective voltage applied in the drift/diffusion active region.

This model can be upgraded with additional physical mechanisms, such as the electrochemical process of oxidation and reduction [23], [24] and detailed ionic transport models, such as ionic hopping [25], to improve the physical accuracy of the model. Also, note that the description of the volatile behavior in this model, namely the Gibbs–Thomson interfacial potential energy in (1), can be considered a physics-based empirical model, thus an accurate description of the volatile dynamics of the resistive switching device, e.g., the relaxation time, is missing.

V. RELAXATION TIME

The relaxation to the OFF-state after switching is a crucial process for the application as crosspoint selector devices, where a fast relaxation is needed to prevent reading error [26]. Relaxation time (or retention time) is also critical for neuromorphic computing applications [27], where the relaxation dynamics can mimic the short-term memory of biological synapses.

To assess the relaxation time of our volatile RRAM devices, we applied the two-pulse experiment in Fig. 4(a), where the first triangular pulse induces a transition to the ON-state while the second triangular pulse probes the state of the device after a variable delay time t_D . During the measurement, a compliance current of 16 μ A was applied by a transistor connected in series to the memory device. The collected current shows that the device still remains in the ON-state after a relatively short delay $t_D = 10$ μ s [Fig. 4(a)] while it is found in the OFF-state after a relatively long $t_D = 10$ ms [Fig. 4(b)]. Fig. 5(a)

TABLE I
MODEL PARAMETER VALUES

Parameter	Forming	After Forming
η	$1.6 \times 10^{-2} \text{ J} \cdot \text{s} \cdot \text{m}^{-2}$	$1.6 \times 10^{-2} \text{ J} \cdot \text{s} \cdot \text{m}^{-2}$
α	$1.8 \times 10^{-17} \text{ C}$	$5.1 \times 10^{-17} \text{ C}$
V_s	0.5 V	1.3 V (+) 0.05V (-)
C_T	$7 \times 10^{15} \text{ K} \cdot \text{W}^{-1} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$	$7 \times 10^{14} \text{ K} \cdot \text{W}^{-1} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$
κ	$1 \times 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$	$1 \times 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$
w_i	100 eV	100 eV
R_t	1.5 nm	2.5 nm
x_C	2.55 nm	2.17 nm
R_i	500 Ω	100 Ω
l_t	1.36 \AA	2.17 \AA
β	10 nm/V	1 nm/V

Fig. 4. AC characteristics of the relaxation time of the volatile switching device for selector application by monitoring the current response of the device when two voltage pulses separated with a variable delay time t_D being applied. (a) Device remains turn on after a short delay time, $t_D = 10 \mu\text{s}$. (b) Device has turned-off after a long delay time, $t_D = 10 \text{ms}$.

Fig. 5. (a) Statistical result of the percentage of the ON-state device at the second pulse after various delay time of the first pulse. The relaxation time is around 1 ms; however, large variation exists. (b) Experimental and calculated turn-on voltages of the second pulse as a function of delay time. The cross markers indicate the median turn-on voltages for positive and/or negative bias. The curves are calculated based on the simulated gap length as a function of delay time for a filament with an initial diameter $\phi_0 = 0.3 \text{nm}$.

summarizes the probability distribution of finding the device in the ON-state device after a delay time t_D . An average retention time around 1 ms can be assessed from these statistical data.

The threshold voltage of the first pulse V_{T1+} and the second pulse V_{T2+} can be collected, as shown in Fig. 4(b), thus allowing to study the evolution of the device during relaxation. The reported threshold voltage V_{T2+} in Fig. 5(b) shows that V_{T2+} is generally smaller than V_{T1+} . This can be understood by the gradual retraction of the Ag NPs back to the electrodes during relaxation. The similar transient behavior is shown by the second threshold voltage V_{T2-} under negative voltage, which is smaller than the first threshold voltage V_{T1-} . Note that V_{T1+} and V_{T1-} in the pulse measurements are higher than the corresponding values in the dc measurements shown in Fig. 2(b), which can be attributed to the finite speed of ionic motion during the switching process. The time-dependent threshold voltage will be discussed further in the companion paper [12] where the filament growth model is shown.

VI. SURFACE DIFFUSION MODEL

A. Molecular Dynamics and Numerical Modeling

To clarify the relaxation dynamics in the volatile RRAM, we conduct molecular dynamics (MD) simulations of the nanoscale metallic Ag filament, using the LAMMPS software package [28] with an embedded-atom method (EAM) potential describing the Ag atom interaction [29]. Fig. 6(a) shows the simulated nanoscale metallic Ag filament at increasing times up to 500 ps at relatively high temperature (800 K) to obtain the filament relaxation in the reasonable simulation time. The simulated filament was initially located between two fixed Ag planar structures serving as the two electrodes. The filament shows a spontaneous disconnection in correspondence to the intermediate point, as a result of the Brownian-like motion of the individual atoms. These simulations suggest that the main driving force for filament relaxation is the minimization of the surface energy, similar to the formation of the liquid drop due to surface tension [30]. This model shares the same physical driving force as the Gibbs–Thomson effect implemented in (1) [31]. The further analysis of the MD simulation results shows that the filament shape evolution is due to the diffusion of Ag atoms at the surface of the filament while the bulk atoms tend to remain in their fixed crystalline lattice positions [31]. Thus, we conclude that the surface tension dominates the spontaneous transition to the OFF-state in our volatile RRAM device.

Note that, in the MD simulations, we assumed the filament atoms surrounded by vacuum for simplicity. If a surrounding material such as HfO_x or SiO_x was assumed, instead, one would have to consider out-diffusion of Ag atoms from the filament to the host material, which has been proposed as a possible model for the spontaneous rupture of the metallic conductive filament (CF) in volatile RRAM [32]. However, this mechanism might be ruled out for Ag-based devices, since transmission electron microscope (TEM) observations suggest that Ag atoms tend to cluster together rather than diffuse to the surrounding dielectric material [33], [34]. At the same time, the out-diffusion of Ag might contribute to endurance failure since a homogenous redistribution of the Ag atoms within dielectric material might fail the resistive switching process of high ON–OFF ratio.

Since the MD simulation is time-consuming, especially at room temperature, we develop a numerical model to describe the relaxation process. In the numerical model, we consider the minimization of the surface energy as the main driving force for the relaxation of the CF [35]. We also assume that only metal atoms on the surface of the CF contribute to the relaxation process, where the diffusion rate is proportional to the gradient of the surface chemical potential [36]. On the other hand, bulk atoms within the CF remain crystallized, as observed by *in situ* TEM in recent reports [33], [34], thus are assumed to remain virtually stable. Since the surface chemical potential is proportional to the surface curvature K ($K = 1/r_1 + 1/r_2$, where r_1 and r_2 are the principal radii of curvature), the effect of surface atom self-diffusion driven by surface-energy minimization is described by the surface

Fig. 6. Simulated shape evolution of Ag CF for the relaxation process. (a) MD simulation of a nanoscale metallic filament between two fixed Ag planar structures at 800 K. (b) Numerical simulation based on the surface diffusion model. The initial filament is assumed to be the shape consisted by two reversed truncated cones, with the conical angle $\theta = 5^\circ$ and the thinnest diameter $\phi_0 = 0.3$ nm. The gap length after the filament disruption is also recorded during the simulation for further analysis.

atomic flux J_s along the surface s [37], [38], namely

$$J_s = -B\nabla_s K. \quad (5)$$

Here, $B = (D_s \gamma \delta^4 / k_B T)$, where D_s is the diffusion coefficient, γ is the surface energy, and δ is the interatomic distance. The diffusion coefficient is thermally activated following Arrhenius law $D_s = D'_s \exp(-E_{\text{surf}} / k_B T)$, where D'_s is a preexponential factor and E_{surf} is the energy barrier for surface diffusion. For simplicity, we assume isotropic surface self-diffusion and cylindrical symmetry of the filament shape. As a result, the CF evolution can be described by the outward normal rate of the surface profile ρ , which is given by [37]

$$\frac{dn}{dt} = -\frac{B}{\rho} \frac{\partial}{\partial s} \left(\rho \frac{\partial K}{\partial s} \right). \quad (6)$$

Fig. 6(b) shows simulation results obtained by numerically solving (6) for times up to 2 ms. The MD and numerical simulations of the shape evolution of the filament reproduce the Ag filament retraction observed by high-resolution TEM [16], [30], [39]. The CF was assumed to consist initially of two truncated cones with the conical angle $\theta = 5^\circ$ and the thinnest diameter $\phi_0 = 0.3$ nm. Note that, due to the assumption of isotropic surface diffusion, the filament shape evolution by numerical simulation [Fig. 6(b)] cannot faithfully reproduce the MD simulations, where Ag diffusion must obey the crystallographic order [Fig. 6(a)]. The simulation results show that the CF first breaks in two pieces, which we refer to as the *disconnection* process. Then, the length g of the gap between the two CF pieces increases with time, which we refer to as the *retraction* process. For the simulations in Fig. 6(b), we assumed Ag parameter values of $D'_s = 2.14 \times 10^{-8}$ m²/s [37], $E_{\text{surf}} = 0.55$ eV [36], $\delta = 2.9$ Å, $\gamma = 1$ J/m² [38], [40], which yield a value of $B \approx 2 \times 10^{-35}$ m⁴/s at room temperature.

Including dielectric materials surrounding the filament, surface diffusivity and surface energy should be replaced

Fig. 7. Gap length of the filament as a function of delay time for different initial diameters from 0.1 to 0.5 nm. Gap length $g = 0$ corresponds to the state where the filament is still continuous.

by interfacial diffusivity and interfacial energy, respectively, which are expected to be comparable to the surface counterparts [31]. This modification may slightly affect the timescale of the filament relaxation process, although the details of the shape evolution of the filament are not expected to change significantly.

B. Simulation Results

Fig. 7 shows the calculated gap length g of the CF as a function of the delay time for different initial diameters from 0.1 to 0.5 nm. Note that, due to the finite size of Ag atoms (~ 2.9 Å), the smaller filament diameters should be interpreted as the effective size of a silver atom chain/cluster. From these results, the relaxation time (t_R) of the volatile RRAM can be taken as the first appearance of a gap length $g > 0$, i.e., filament break time, marking the transition to the OFF-state. The relaxation time of the device varies in a broad range from 10 μs to 10 ms, as the CF size changes over a relatively small range from 0.1 to 0.5 nm. In particular, the calculated relaxation time for a CF diameter of $\phi_0 = 0.4$ nm is around 1 ms, which well describes the median relaxation time of the device shown in Fig. 5(a). Cycle-to-cycle variations

Fig. 8. Simulated filament break time as a function of its initial filament diameter, following well with the Herring's scaling law.

of the relaxation time in the figure can thus be explained by minimal changes of the initial diameter (or the conical angle [31]), which have a strong impact on the relaxation dynamics, as shown in Fig. 7.

During the retraction time, the threshold voltages V_{T2+} and V_{T2-} can be used as a monitor of the gap length, as the switching process is driven by the electric field. For instance, V_{T2+} can be estimated by

$$V_{T2+} = \frac{V_{T1+}}{g_m} g \quad (7)$$

where g_m is the maximum gap length in the OFF-state. A similar relationship can be assumed for V_{T2-} . Fig. 5(b) shows the calculated V_{T2+} and V_{T2-} as a function of time, assuming a CF diameter $\phi_0 = 0.3$ nm. A maximum gap length $g_m = 4.8$ nm was assumed for the OFF-state. From Fig. 5(b), the increase of V_{T2+} with time can be well described by the increasing gap length. The large variation of the retention time might also be caused by the variation of the size of the formed filament or the activation energy E_{surf} .

Fig. 8 summarizes the calculated relaxation time, t_R , i.e., simulated filament break time, as a function of ϕ_0 , according to the results shown in Fig. 7. The relaxation time of a cylindrical filament is also shown for comparison. The calculations show a power-law behavior with an exponent of about 4. This is consistent with the Herring's law $\lambda_t \sim \lambda_\phi^4$ [41], stating that the scaling factor λ_t of the time needed for a geometrical change induced by surface diffusion scales proportionally with the fourth power of the size scaling factor λ_ϕ . This strong size dependence can give guidance to the optimized performance of the volatile RRAM. For instance, in the application as a selector device, both high ON-current and short relaxation time are needed. However, these two requirements are conflicting to each other as a large ON-current requires a large ϕ_0 , which however, also causes a relatively long relaxation time. Materials engineering, such as the multi-filamentary switching induced by defected graphene layer at the Ag/insulator interface [39], might solve this dilemma, for the development of RRAM-based selector devices in crosspoint arrays.

VII. CONCLUSION

We present a comprehensive physics-based modeling framework for volatile RRAM devices based on Ag filament. A thermally activated drift-diffusion model with the Monte Carlo approach can account for the forming and switching characteristics of our volatile RRAM. MD simulations and a numerical surface-diffusion model are shown to accurately capture the relaxation dynamics of the volatile RRAM, which is explained by the surface energy minimization. The relaxation time is shown to depend strongly on the CF size, thus enabling a better understanding of retention variations and design window for the selector and neuromorphic devices based on volatile RRAM.

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